

Conference Abstract

Latest observations on the nesting of the black stork *Ciconia nigra* Linnaeus, 1758 (Aves Ciconiidae) in valle del Vitravo (Calabria, Italia)

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Received: 20 Sep 2019 | Published: 24 Sep 2019

Citation: Lamanna F, Dima C (2019) Latest observations on the nesting of the black stork *Ciconia nigra* Linnaeus, 1758 (Aves Ciconiidae) in valle del Vitravo (Calabria, Italia). ARPHA Conference Abstracts 2: e46734. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.2.e46734>

Abstract

This work contains the latest observations on the Black Stork nesting in the Site of National Importance, Vitravo Valley, in central and eastern Calabria. The data acquired relates to the 2019 breeding season during which a monitoring was conducted on the nesting site and throughout the area of highest frequency of the species. The research allowed to ascertain the couple in the reproductive phase, with the failed hatching of the laid eggs and to record the constant presence of a sub-adult specimen in the nesting area.

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Presented at

Vth International Congress on Biodiversity: „Taxonomy, Speciation and Euro-Mediterranean Biodiversity“